

HOW TO COMPLY WITH NPR 7150.2 AND GET REAL WORK DONE

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NPR 7150.2

NASA Procedural Requirements

COMPLIANCE IS MANDATORY FOR NASA EMPLOYEES

NPR 7150.2D

Effective Date: March 08, 2022
Expiration Date: March 08, 2027

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- 2,000 pages (back of the envelope)

KOSMA Translator Software Development Plan

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VERIFY THAT THIS IS THE CORRECT REVISION BEFORE USE

ziggy

Ziggy SMP (27 pages)

A grid of 27 thumbnail images representing pages from the Ziggy Software Management Plan (SMP). The thumbnails are arranged in a 4x7 grid, with the last row containing only 3 thumbnails. Each thumbnail shows a different page from the document, including:

- Page 1: Title page with NASA logo and project name.
- Page 2: Table of Contents.
- Page 3: Introduction and Summary.
- Page 4: Overview.
- Page 5: Software Management Requirements.
- Page 6: Software Life Cycle Planning.
- Page 7: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 8: Software Development Process and Product.
- Page 9: Software Risk Management.
- Page 10: Software Requirements.
- Page 11: Software Architecture.
- Page 12: Software Design.
- Page 13: Software Implementation.
- Page 14: Software Testing.
- Page 15: Software Operations, Maintenance, and Evaluation.
- Page 16: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 17: Software Release.
- Page 18: Software Plan Review/Sign-off.
- Page 19: Software Management.
- Page 20: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 21: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 22: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 23: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 24: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 25: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 26: Software Configuration Management.
- Page 27: Software Configuration Management.

Sample SMP Section

3.3 Software Schedules

This section claims compliance with the following NPR 7150.2 requirement(s):

SWE-016: The project manager shall document and maintain a software schedule that satisfies the following conditions:

- a. Coordinates with the overall project schedule.
- b. Documents the interactions of milestones and deliverables between software, hardware, operations, and the rest of the system.
- c. Reflects the critical dependencies for software development activities.
- d. Identifies and accounts for dependencies with other projects and cross-program dependencies.

SWE-018: The project manager shall regularly hold reviews of software schedule activities, metrics, status, and results with the project stakeholders and track issues to resolution.

SWE-046: The project manager shall require the software developer(s) to provide a software schedule for the project's review and schedule updates as requested.

The [Ziggy schedule](#) is implemented in [Jira](#). It is described in Appendix B, [Jira Workflow](#).

The Software Review Board (SRB) meets regularly to define releases and dependencies, estimate work, and update the schedule. See Section 5.1, [Software Configuration Management](#), for more information about the SRB.

To ensure issues are resolved and metrics obtained, each release (epic) in Jira contains VDD and FCA tabs that capture this information. See Section 4.4, [Software Implementation](#), and Section 4.6, [Software Operations, Maintenance, and Retirement](#) for details.

Automatic Gantt Chart

Document Workflow

Development Workflow

Bi-Directional Traceability via Requirements Artifacts Tab

Details Analysis **Artifacts**

Requirement Source
Higher level external requirement. Use a paragraph ID and description if available. May be None to indicate that this is a top level requirement or See Parent [link](#) if a Parent link is present.

Design Document
Name of class, package, or other file or Design field in a Jira issue.

Component
Name of class, package, or other file or program.

Verification Test
Unit test (class), test procedure, or list of steps used to verify this issue. Requirements shall specify a unit test or test procedure.

Manual
Name of manual or Markdown file.

Custom Fields

Design

The detailed design provides enough information for someone to create code without significant interpretation (see also [Software Engineering Handbook](#)).

Verification Test

Unit test (class), test procedure, or list of steps used to verify this issue. Requirements shall specify a unit test or test procedure.

Regression Test

Consider any code the new code touches and list existing test procedures or unit tests (classes) that cover that code.

Resolution Checklists

Resolution* Fixed ?

Assignee Bill Wohler ?

Version

Relevant Git commit or Confluence version for this issue.

Resolution* Fixed ?

Assignee Bill Wohler ?

Resolution Checklist

- Listed design notes capture the as-built design and all comments have been resolved
- User manual is updated if necessary
- Code compiles
- Tests pass
- Code coverage is same or greater as previous version
- Current code coverage is added to comment
- Output of gradlew check is added to comment

All items shall be performed before resolving an issue.

Testing Redlines & Comments

 [Bill Wohler](#) added a comment - 2024-03-29T15:38 - edited

ZiggyConsoleTest

In the parameters panel, we used the copy command to make a copy. The name we entered was ignored and a "Copy of Algorithm Parameters" was created. Filed [ZIGGY-418](#), Copy command behaves inconsistently.

Updated procedures to say that the dialogs should be saved, not canceled.

Epic's TRR Tab

Details **TRR** Test Report VDD FCA

Epic Contains Issues	<input type="text" value="Yes No [- Comment]"/> All Jira issues for this release have been added to the epic.
Resolution Checklists Complete	<input type="text" value="Yes No [- Comment]"/> Ensure that all issues in the epic have a complete resolution checklist. For example, the query to view all issues for the Ziggy 0.2.0 release is "Epic Link" = ZIGGY-56 . Add Resolution Checklist to displayed columns to identify missing items.
Unit Tests Pass	<input type="text" value="Yes No [- Comment]"/> Include output of <code>./gradlew</code> check in comment.
Static Analysis Reviewed	<input type="text" value="Yes No [- Comment]"/> Static analysis has been performed and all high priority errors have been corrected. Include output of <code>./gradlew</code> check in comment.

This is a Better Way

In Sum

- The Ziggy SMP/process is lightweight

In Sum

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- Adaptable for Class C missions

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Thank you!

Diving into More Details

The background features a dark blue gradient with a subtle pattern of white stars and technical diagrams. On the right side, there are several circular diagrams: a large one with concentric circles and a scale from 80 to 210, and a smaller one below it with dashed lines and arrows. On the left, there are partial circular diagrams with arrows. The overall aesthetic is clean and technical.

Jira Issue

Jira Software Dashboards ▾ Projects ▾ Issues ▾ Boards ▾ Structure ▾ Plans ▾ **Create**

 Ziggy / ZIGGY-315
Command-line interface

 Add comment Assign More ▾ **Approved for Work ▾** Admin ▾

▼ **Details**

Type: Requirement Resolution: Unresolved
Priority: Medium
Component/s: None
Labels: [operator-interface](#)

Details **Analysis** Artifacts

Correct:	Yes
Consistent:	Yes
Clear:	Yes
Complete:	Yes
Traceable:	Yes
Feasible:	Yes
Verifiable:	Yes
Maintainable:	Yes

▼ **Description**
Ziggy shall provide a command-line interface.

Impact Analysis Tab

Details	Impact Analysis
Stakeholders	<input type="text" value="TODO"/>
Schedule and Cost	<input type="text" value="TODO"/> Impact on schedule and cost (including making and testing the change).
Software	<input type="text" value="TODO"/> Impact on existing software (functions, features, and interfaces) and systems. Also consider that existing software may have to be refactored. Kent Beck says, "make the change easy (warning: this may be hard), then make the easy change."
Baseline Products	<input type="text" value="TODO"/> Impact on other baseline products, such as architecture, design, tests, and documentation.
Risk	<input type="text" value="TODO"/> Risk of making the change vs. not making it.
Size	<input type="text" value="TODO"/> Small, Medium, or Large.
Complexity	<input type="text" value="TODO"/> Trivial, Normal, or Complex.

Test Plan

 Bill Wohler added a comment - 2024-02-13T14:26 - edited

The test procedures and verification tests that are required to verify this release should be performed in the following order.

Test	Status
ZiggyBuildTest	Pass
ZIGGY-126	Pass
ZiggyUnitTest	Pass
ZIGGY-371	Pass
ZIGGY-378	Pass
ZIGGY-381	Pass
ZIGGY-382	Pass
ZiggyClusterTest (1)	Pass
ZiggyClusterTest (2)	Pass w/comments
ZIGGY-391	Pass
ZIGGY-392	Pass
ZiggySamplePipelineTest (1)	Pass w/comments and redlines
ZIGGY-299 (1)	Pass

Epic's Test Report Tab

Location/s

List one or more locations of the test participants.

Tested

All of the issues in the epic are in the Tested state (except for issues of type Documentation).

Summary of Test Results

Detailed Test Results

List verified requirements, describe problems with verification or regression tests, list deviations from test procedures (redlines), and list issues created.

Epic's VDD Tab

SMP Version	<input type="text" value="0"/>	Determine version of Software Management Plan used from Confluence Menu > Page History.
Test Procedures Version	<input type="text" value="0"/>	Determine version of Test Procedures used from Confluence Menu > Page History.
Lines of Code	<input type="text" value="0"/>	The total lines of code, which can be determined in the Ziggy root directory with <code>cloc --vcs=git . awk '/^SUM:/{print \$5}'</code> .
Code Coverage	<input type="text" value="0"/>	List percentage in current release. To determine this value, run <code>./gradle check</code> and view <code>build/reports/jacoco/test/html/index.html</code> .
Open Issues	<input type="text" value="TODO"/>	Add query for Jira issues that remained open after the release. Use <code>project = ZIGGY AND (status != Resolved AND status != Closed OR resolved >= YYYY-MM-DD)</code> , where the date is obtained from the epic's Resolved field.

Epic's FCA Tab

Details TRR Test Report VDD **FCA**

Architecture Complete	<input type="text" value="Yes No, Version, Date"/> See Ziggy Software Architectural Design Specification (NAS-Ziggy-ARCH-001).
Test Procedures Complete	<input type="text" value="Yes No, Version, Date"/> See Ziggy Verification & Validation Plan and Procedures (NAS-Ziggy-VV-001).
User Manual Complete	<input type="text" value="Yes No, Commit, Date of Commit"/> See ziggy/doc/user-manual .
Design Complete	<input type="text" value="Yes No [- Comment]"/> Ensure that all issues in the epic have a complete design field. For example, the query to determine issues without a design for the Ziggy 0.2.0 release is <code>project = ZIGGY AND "Epic Link" = ZIGGY-56 AND type != Bug AND (Design is EMPTY OR Design ~ "TODO")</code> .
Design Review Complete	<input type="text" value="Yes No [- Comment]"/> Ensure that all issues in the epic have had a design review. For example, the query to determine unreviewed issues for the Ziggy 0.2.0 release is <code>project = ZIGGY AND "Epic Link" = ZIGGY-56 AND type != Bug AND ("Design Review" is EMPTY OR "Design Review" ~ "TODO")</code> .

Jira Workflow

Appendix B. Jira Workflow

The following Jira elements are employed by the Ziggy team in addition to the common Summary, Description, and Comment fields:

- Releases are associated with the Epic type.
- Issues that make up the release have the Story, used for features or enhancements, or Bug type.
- Operations and other activities that do not include modifying source code have the Task type.
- Labels help with Jira queries. Recommended labels are discussed below.
- The Original Estimate is used to generate the schedule.
- The Priority should be set as described below.
- The appropriate Component(s) should be selected.
- Links of type "has to be done before/after" are created to set up dependencies between releases and operations.

Before development on a release begins, the LRE creates a Jira epic to track the release and sets the Summary to "Ziggy m.n.p" as described in Section 4.4, [Software Implementation](#). The LRE, in collaboration with the SRB, links the Jira issues that should go into this release via the Epic Link field.

Git Workflow – Release Branches

Release Branches

The goals that define the release branch process are twofold. First, as noted above, the stable branch must always be kept in a production-ready state; therefore, the changes that are to be incorporated into a release can only be merged to stable after all testing has been performed. Second, during testing of the release codebase, the branch used for testing must represent exactly the content of the ultimate release branch; therefore, the stable branch must be merged into the release branch before testing begins.

Releases are numbered m.n.p, where m, n, and p refer to the major, minor, and patch number for the release. It is the responsibility of the Lead Release Engineer (LRE) to manage release branches.

1. Create release branch at the beginning of the release cycle. This is performed from within the release's Jira epic by clicking on the Development > Create branch link. Choose the Release branch type and branch from the stable branch, or from a current release branch that hasn't yet been merged to stable. Use the branch name that Bitbucket provides.
2. Wait until all of the epic's issues have been resolved and their feature branches have been merged (see [Feature Branches](#)).
3. Ensure that stable is up to date and that any new commits in stable are merged to the release branch. Note that there shouldn't be any new commits on stable if step 13 is followed.

```
$ git fetch
$ git checkout stable
$ git merge --no-edit
$ git checkout release/ZIGGY-#-ziggy-m.n.p
$ git merge --no-edit --no-ff stable
```

4. Perform a dry run of all required tests. If testing uncovers defects, follow instructions in step 10.
5. Edit `gradle.properties` and update `version` to m.n.p.
6. Edit `CITATION.cff` and update `version` to vm.n.p and `date-released` to YYYY-MM-DD.
7. Edit `RELEASE-NOTES.md` and add appropriate notes for the release. The text will be used verbatim when creating the GitHub release.
8. Create a release candidate on the release branch. The merge ensures that an existing local branch is up to date. The changes just made are then committed before the tag is made.